

Use of high potential secondary thermal energy resources

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Annotation

The article analyzes the "secondary energy resources" in the industry of Uzbekistan, explores their operation and use. A new heat exchanger scheme for the use of secondary thermal energy resources has been introduced.

Introduction

The Republic of Uzbekistan is a country with sufficient primary energy resources. At present, its energy resources exceed the domestic demand by 15-20%. However, like the trend of energy consumption around the world, there is a shortage of energy for the rapidly developing industry of Uzbekistan.

Therefore, the efficient use of thermal energy resources is becoming a topical issue in modern manufacturing industry, life expectancy. The use of secondary energy sources is effective in order to save primary-primary energy resources. These are: renewable (non-conventional) energy types (QTEM); secondary thermal energy resources (IIER).

The main part

A number of regulatory documents have been adopted by the state on the use of QTEMs. In particular, the law "On rational use of energy" was adopted on April 25, 1997. The Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 13, 2009 states "The basis for the use of non-traditional and renewable energy in ensuring energy security of the country for 2009-2013. There

are certain scientific works, developments (1) and practical works in this field.

It is difficult to say the same about IIER. Secondary thermal energy resources (IIER) - combustion products (smoke gases) emitted into the atmosphere from products, wastes, satellites and intermediate products - from technological units, devices and technological parts - can no longer be used in this case, but can be used elsewhere and for other purposes heat potential.

More than half of the mined fuel, 65% of the electricity generated, is consumed by industrial enterprises. Their fuel heat efficiency is low. Fuel heat utilization rate (FHF) in advanced industrial enterprises does not exceed 40%. For example, 190 tons of flue gases with a temperature of 400 0C per hour are released into the environment from 1 compressor unit of the main gas pipeline compressor stations.

The table shows the secondary energy resources (IER) generated in the most energy-intensive industries of Uzbekistan and the state of their use (million tons of conventional fuel).

Table 1. Use of IER (million tons of conventional fuel) in energy-intensive industries.

Analysis of the data in the table shows that the Uzbek industry has huge secondary energy resources and their use is very low.

Thus, in order to use such energy resources, it is expedient to create energy-saving technologies, the use of efficient heat exchangers.

One way to use IIER would be to use air heaters.

Figure 1 shows a low-cost modernized circuit of this air heater, cooling the intermediate heat carrier.

Figure 1. 1- dispersed intermediate heat carrier, 2- intermediate heat carrier downward moving pipes, 3- edged heat pipes mounted on the surface of the pipe, 4- barrier, 5- water corridors, 6- cooling chamber, 7- grate, 8- conveyor, 9- heating chamber.

The apparatus works as follows: in the heating chamber (9) above, the dispersed intermediate heat carrier (1) is heated by means of high-temperature flue gases. Exhaust fumes are released from the chamber into the atmosphere (not shown in the figure). The intermediate heat carrier slides tightly into the lower cooling chamber (6) through pipes (2) mounted under the upper chamber. The cooling chamber is divided into a grate (7) and a grate (7) mounted under the pipe (2). the dispersed material is returned to the upper chamber again using a conveyor (9). The compressed air supplied from below moves against the dispersed material and heats up.

The air moving through the dispersed material inside the pipe is removed through a tube corridor mounted on top of the cooling chamber and sent to the consumer.

A water heating system is designed in the upper part of the cooling chamber. Cold

water is moved through special corridors (pictured schematically) by the outside of the pipes separating the dispersed material, which is heated and sent to consumption by means of edged heat pipes installed in it.

Conclusion

The peculiarity of this scheme is that, if necessary, the side mounted on the air barrier (4) can be inserted into the space between the edged (not shown) pipes and heated using a heat pipe. The application of the proposed heat exchanger accelerates the heat exchange process, increasing the F.I.K. of the device.

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